

Comparative Analysis Of Forecasting Unemployment Rate In Pakistan Using Different Univariate Time Series Models

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DOI: <https://doi.org/>

Keywords

Unemployment Rate,
Forecasting, Univariate Time
Series Models, Model
Selection Criteria.

Article History

Received on 10 Feb 2026

Accepted on 15 Mar 2026

Published on 24 Mar 2026

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Abstract

Forecasting unemployment is important for policymakers because it assists them in planning for job creation and supporting economic growth. This study compares the performance of three time series models Brown's Double Exponential Smoothing, Holt's Linear Exponential Smoothing, and the ARIMA model in predicting Pakistan's unemployment rate. In this study yearly unemployment data from 1986 to 2023 was sourced from the Trading Economics website. The two validation approaches in-sample and out-of-sample, together with two data-splitting ratios - 80/20 and 70/30 were used for the evaluation of models. Each model was applied twice. The model performance evaluation is based on the error measure of out-of-sample data to choose the finest model using four accuracy metrics Mean Absolute Error, Mean Squared Error, Mean Absolute Percentage Error, and Root Mean Squared Error. After the analyses the most appropriate model is Brown Exponential Smoothing which reveals best performance in forecasting the unemployment rate in Pakistan as it signified the minimum value of all error measures. According to Brown's model, the unemployment rate of Pakistan is probable to gradually decline during the period from 2015 to 2018. These results suggest that simple forecasting methods can provide results that are both accurate and easy to apply. These findings provide policymakers with evidence-based useful guidance for planning job creation strategies, training programs, and labor market strategies.

Introduction

Unemployment is when a person is fit and willing to work but cannot get a job. Unemployment is one of the key measures of the Macroeconomic status of a country. dividing the total of individuals jobless by the total workforce is commonly formula for calculation of unemployment rate, which is measured by the workforce comprises both people who are doing job and those who are not but are available and looking for jobs. A high unemployment rate indicates weak labor market conditions, while a low rate shows stronger economic movement.

$$\text{Unemployment rate} = \frac{\text{no of unemployed people}}{\text{total labor force}} * 100$$

The unemployment rate is widely used as the key indicator of labour market conditions. (Reserve Bank of Australia). The unemployment rate is not constantly consistent over time due to different macroeconomic factors distressing it. To predict the annual unemployment rate, it requires a new and correct forecasting models gradually, to forecast the yearly unemployment rate. Unemployment is a key macroeconomic factor that reflects the condition of an economic balance of country and is a hurdle to social development (Dritsakis & Klazoglou, 2018). According to Ruth et al. (2014), A person of working age who wants a full-time work but is incapable to get one is considered unemployed, Unintentional and unpaid are the two main categories of unemployment. In developed countries, labour market models are used to predict how many workers will be needed in different jobs (Błaszczewicz, 2015; Gruchociak, 2013). This helps people prepare for future work in advance and can lower unemployment caused by a gap between workers' skills and job needs. Unemployment has many negative effects, such as harming the economy, increasing crime, wasting people's talents, causing depression, and creating fear and insecurity in society (Kyei & Gyeke, 2011).

In Pakistan the unemployment continues to be one of the most serious challenges and has been increasing over time in Pakistan. Many issues contribute to unemployment, such as limited job opportunities, lack of investment, and mismatch between education and labor market needs. A large number of graduates face difficulties finding jobs and many people cannot meet their basic needs due to joblessness. If both the government and private sectors collaborate to create more employment opportunities and offer young graduates development skills programs, the unemployment situation in Pakistan could gradually improve. Forecasting the unemployment rate is important for policymakers because it assists them in planning and taking precautionary measures before unemployment rises further. Forecasting means using historical data and statistical methods to estimate what will happen in the future. However, forecasts do not always match the exact outcomes; that is why continuous improvement of forecasting methods is necessary. In many fields, including economic planning, forecasting supports effective and efficient decision-making. To forecast unemployment, different statistical models are used and comparing these models helps decision-makers choose the best method. Standard models include the Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA), Brown's Double Exponential Smoothing, and Holt's Linear Exponential Smoothing Model. Policymakers can identify the most reliable approach and use it to set up better arrangements to reduce unemployment in Pakistan by comparing the estimates from these models. From 1986 to 2023 the unemployment statistics has been used. The dataset was portion into two parts: out-of-sample validation and an in-sample set for model estimation. Forecasts were then produced for the years 2024–2030. The precision of these forecasts was estimated

using Mean Absolute Error, Mean Squared Error, Mean Absolute Percentage Error and Root Mean Squared Error.

1.2 Research Gap:

- Several studies have compared different univariate models for forecasting unemployment in countries like the USA, Tanzania, and Malaysia. So far, there is no published research in Pakistan that compares multiple univariate time series models such as Brown's Double Exponential Smoothing, Holt's Linear Exponential Smoothing, and ARIMA for forecasting unemployment.
- Most studies in Pakistan have used only regression or a single forecasting model. Therefore, it remains unclear which univariate model performs best for predicting Pakistan's unemployment rate.

1.3 Research Hypotheses

- H_0 : There is no significant difference in forecasting accuracy among Holt's Linear, Brown's Double Exponential, and ARIMA models.
- H_1 : There is a significant difference in forecasting accuracy among these models.

1.4 Study Objectives:

- Using different time series models to estimate and compare for unemployment rate of Pakistan.
- To choose the best model based on in-sample and out-of-sample forecast accuracy measures of all three models.
- It purposes to forecast the Pakistan's unemployment rate in the study for seven years periods from 2024 to 2030.

2.Literature Review

Vizie & Kamarudin (2024) demonstrated the yearly unemployment rate of Malaysia using Artificial Neural Networks, Autoregressive Integrated Moving Averages, and Holt's Exponential Smoothing approach. The performance of the model was evaluated using the RMSE and MAPE values. To forecast Malaysia's unemployment rate for the following five years, a total of 39 data points from 1982 to 2020 were collected. A training and testing set were used as to estimate prediction accuracy. In the study showed that ANN performs better than ARIMA (0,1,1) and Holt's Exponential Smoothing approach in forecasting Malaysia's unemployment rate. 7.47 % is a value MAPE of and 0.47% is a value of RMSE which indicate the Holts is best and accurate.

Tengaa et al. (2023) conducted research to create a forecasting method for unemployment rate of Tanzania and give decision-makers a useful tool. Unemployment forecasting is dynamic for informed governmental, mainly in countries like Tanzania. Integrated Moving Average) model. Using a non-probability sampling strategy, the complete dataset available for the designated period is used. To help take the best model, diagnostic tests such as unit root analysis, Auto Correlation Function, and Partial Auto Correlation Function carried out. Differencing eliminates non stationarity from the time line data by eliminating trend and seasonality effects. The ideal model choice was based on criteria such as AIC (Akaike Information Criterion), Schwartz, and Hannan-Quinn.

Chia Xin Yi and Khalid (2022) clarified that unemployment is one of the greatest issues for both created and creating nations. An important indicator of how well a nation is producing jobs is its unemployment rate. In their review, they pointed out that most past studies focused on predicting three-monthly or annual unemployment rates using methods like Simple Exponential Smoothing, Holt's Linear

Exponential Smoothing, and ARIMA models. However, very few studies have looked at forecasting the monthly unemployment rate in Malaysia, even though it can give quicker information for decision-making. To fill this gap, their study compared three methods the, Holt's Linear Exponential Smoothing model, Naive model and the Box Jenkins model. They showed that selecting the right model is important and that accuracy can be checked with measures like Mean Absolute Percentage Error, Mean Square Error & Mean Absolute Deviation. Their work also showed that in some cases, even simple models can work well. **Gostkowski and Rokicki (2021)** emphasized that predicting the unemployment rate is very important because it helps governments design better policies and make informed decisions. In their study, they compared several forecasting methods, including the, regression models, Naive method, ARIMA, Holts model, and Winters' model, using data from the Central Statistical Office. They found that while many of these methods can give accurate forecast and found the quadratic regression model and Winters' multiplicative model the best. Their work highlights that forecasting unemployment, although difficult, can be a valuable tool for economic planning and can support labor market institutions in monitoring and improving employment conditions.

3. Methodology

3.1 Data Description

The variable taken in this study is the unemployment rate, which is expressed as a percentage. It covers a total of 38 data points, spanning from 1986 to 2023. It utilizes annual data which is obtained from the Trading Economics website, which provides reliable and up-to-date economic statistics for Pakistan.

3.2 Software

The following software tools were used for analysis and forecasting:

- SPSS was applied for the modeling and forecasting of Holt's Linear Exponential Smoothing and Brown's Double Exponential Smoothing.
- Minitab and EViews used for developing ARIMA models, performing diagnostic tests (stationarity, residual checks), and validating forecasting performance.

3.3 Model Validation Approaches

To accurately evaluate the exactness of forecasts and help comparison, the data has been separated into dual methodologies: in-sample and out-of-sample, using 80/20 and 70/30 split ratios. For the 80/20 split, the initial 30 observations were utilized to produce models and forecasts, while the remaining 08 values were used to measure the accuracy of these forecasts. Similarly, for the 70/30 dataset, eleven observations were used to evaluate the exactness of forecasts after the first 27 values were used to build models and forecasts. Testing with out-of-sample data is very important because it shows how fit the model can predict new data, which is useful for planning and making decisions about the economy. Using these two approaches to check the performance of the models in different situations, ensures the forecasts are accurate and reliable.

3.4 Univariate Forecasting Models:

3.4.1. Brown's Double Exponential Smoothing Model

Brown's Double Exponential Smoothing, often referred to as Brown Linear Exponential Smoothing, is a form of double exponential smoothing that depend on two distinct smoothed series calculated at different times. Using these two components, the model estimates both the level and the trend of the series with only one smoothing parameter (α). The formulas are as follows:

First Smoothing $S'_t = \alpha Y_t + (1 - \alpha)S'_{t-1}$ (1)

Second Smoothing $S''_t = \alpha s'_t + (1 - \alpha)S''_{t-1}$ (2)

Forecast Calculation: -we calculate the forecast components

Level: - $L_t = 2s'_t - s''_t$ (3)

Trend: - $T_t = \frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}(s'_t - s''_t)$ (4)

the forecast for m periods is $\hat{y}_{t+m} = L_{t+} + mT_t$ (5)

where α_t is the estimated level at time t, and T_t is the estimated trend at time t,

S'_t : The first value of double exponential smoothing

s''_t : The second value of double exponential smoothing

m : The number of future periods.

3.4.2) Holt's Linear Exponential Smoothing Model

The Holt model provides increased flexibility in selecting parameter values, which can join both the trend and slopes. the Holt's model uses a single smoothing parameter to predict the trend and base level of time series. A second smoothing parameter for the trend is added to the model to increase forecast accuracy Three basic equations make up Holt's approach, which calculates the trend estimate and the exponential smoothed series.

Holt's method has three fundamental equations that determine the series with exponential smoothing and the forecast of the trend. The equations of Holt's linear exponential model are expressed as follows.

The Level Equation

$$S_t = \alpha y_t - (1 - \alpha)(S_{t-1} + T_{t-1}) \quad (6)$$

Trend Equation

$$T_t = \beta(S_t - S_{t-1}) + (1 - \beta)T_{t-1} \quad (7)$$

The forecast equation

$$\hat{F}_{t+m} = S_t + T_t * m \quad (8)$$

In these equations, S_t shows the estimated level of the series at time t while T_t represents the estimated trend (slope) at the same time.

The forecast for m periods is given by $\hat{F}_{t+m} = S_t + T_t * m$. The α and β are smoothing parameters range between zero and one, and they determine the relative weight assigned to recent observations compared historical data when estimating the level and trend.

3.4.3) Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA)

ARIMA, or Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average, is a method that provides a set of tools for forecasting, estimating parameters, and identifying univariate time series models. ARIMA models are often stated to as Box-Jenkins models after the pioneering work of Box and Jenkins (1976). Earlier, Box and Tiao (1975) introduced the general transfer function model, which became part of the ARIMA framework.

The ARIMA equation is a type of regression equation that involves using forecast errors as independent variables and/or lags of the dependent variable.

An ARIMA model is represented as ARIMA (p, d, q), Where

p (Auto-Regressive part): dependence on previous values of the series (lags).

d (Integrated part): how many times the data is differenced to accomplish stationarity.

q (Moving Average part): dependence on past forecast errors.

The general form of the ARIMA model can be stated as:

$$y_t^{(d)} = c + \epsilon_t + \phi_1 y_{t-1}^{(d)} + \phi_2 y_{t-2}^{(d)} + \dots + \phi_p y_{t-p}^{(d)} + \theta_1 \epsilon_{t-1} + \theta_2 \epsilon_{t-2} + \dots + \theta_p \epsilon_{t-q} \quad (9)$$

In the equation above, $y_t^{(d)}$ represents the differenced series, θ_1 represents the first AR term's coefficient, p represents the AR term's order, θ_1 represents the first MA term's coefficient, q

represents the MA term's order, and ε_t represents the error.

In the equation above, y'_t represents the differenced series, θ_1 represents the first AR term's coefficient, p represents the AR term's order, θ_1 represents the first MA term's coefficient, q represents the MA term's order, and ε_t represents the error.

3.4.3.1) Stationary Checks

The ADF test inspects for stationarity by using the alternative hypothesis that the data is stationary and the null hypothesis that it is not. A p-value derived from the ADF analysis that is less than 0.05 suggests more indication to support the conclusion that the data is not stationary.

3.4.3.2) Box-Jenkins Methodology

The Box-Jenkins technique offers an organized way to construct ARIMA models. Identification, estimation, and diagnostic checking are its three primary steps; forecasting comes next.

3.5 Accuracy Measures

The accuracy with which a forecasting model predicts future values is assessed using error measures. They show the discrepancy between the actual and predicted rates of unemployment. Common accuracy measures include Mean Absolute Error, Mean Squared Error, Root Mean Squared Error, and Mean Absolute Percentage Error. Smaller values of these errors show more accurate and reliable forecasts, chosen to identify which model performs best.

1.The Mean Absolute Error (MAE): The Mean Absolute Error is a common metric for determining forecast accuracy. It calculates the average of the absolute differences between the predicted values and the actual observed values. It expresses us how much the forecasts are, on average, off from the actual values, regardless of direction (over or under).

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n |y_t - \hat{y}_t|$$

2.Mean Squared Error (MSE): -Mean Squared Error is calculation as the average of the squared differences between predicted and actual values. Squaring the errors gives greater importance to larger mistakes, meaning that significant errors impact the MSE more than smaller errors do. A smaller MSE indicates that the model is more accurate.

$$MSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n (y_t - \hat{y}_t)^2$$

3.The Root of Mean Square Error (RMSE):

-The Root Mean Squared Error is a frequently applied for measuring the exactness of a forecasting model. It calculates the square root of the average of the squared differences between forecasted and actual values. RMSE highlights higher errors by squaring them, making it more complex to outliers than MAE.

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n |y_t - \hat{y}_t|^2}$$

4.Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE):-

The Mean Absolute Percentage Error is a normally applied for evaluate the accuracy of a forecasting model. It expresses forecast errors as a percentage of the actual values, enabling interpretation and comparison across various datasets or models.

$$MAPE = 100 * \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n \frac{|y_t - \hat{y}_t|}{Y_t}$$

Results And Discussion

Table 1. Historical Data on The Rate of Unemployment in Pakistan for 38 Years

Peri ods	Ye ar	Unempl oyment rate	Peri ods	Ye ar	Unempl oyment rate
1	1986	3.7	20	2005	7.7
2	1987	3.6	21	2006	7.7
3	1988	3.1	22	2007	6.2
4	1989	3.1	23	2008	5.3
5	1990	3.1	24	2009	5.2
6	1991	3.1	25	2010	5.5
7	1992	6.3	26	2011	5.6
8	1993	5.9	27	2012	6
9	1994	4.7	28	2013	6.2
10	1995	4.8	29	2014	6
11	1996	5.4	30	2015	5.9
12	1997	5.4	31	2016	5.9
13	1998	6.1	32	2017	5.8
14	1999	5.9	33	2018	5.8
15	2000	5.9	34	2019	6.9
16	2001	7.8	35	2020	6.6
17	2002	7.8	36	2021	6.3
18	2003	8.3	37	2022	5.6
19	2004	8.3	38	2023	5.7

STATISTIC	VALUE
Min	3.1
Max	8.3
Mean	5.71
S. D	1.39
Skewness	-0.27
Kurtosis	-0.11
Durbin-Watson test	0.4

The table Above describes the descriptive results the unemployment rate in Pakistan from 1986 to 2023 ranged between 3.1 and 8.3, the mean value of 5.71 with a standard deviation of 1.39 shows that the unemployment rate each year stayed fairly close to the average. The skewness value of -0.27 indicates a small left skewness, whereas the kurtosis value of -0.11 suggests that the distribution is approximately normal with no weighty outliers or heavy tails. The Durbin–Watson statistic of 0.4 reveals strong positive autocorrelation in the time series, intimates that succeeding unemployment values are highly correlated. which confirms the presence of time dependency in the data. Therefore, the usage of time series forecasting models for instance Exponential Smoothing and ARIMA is appropriate for capturing both the level and trend components of the unemployment succession.

Figure 1. Histogram of unemployment rate from 1986 to 2023.

4.2 Descriptive Statistics

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of Unemployment Rate (1986–2023)

Figure 2:-Time Series Plot of The Unemployment Rate From 1986 To 2023

70/30	In -	0.4	8.53	0.7	.856
	Sam- ple	90	1	33	
	Out- Of- Sam	0.4	8.05	0.3	0.58
	ple	78	0	40	3

4.3 Model Estimation and Validation: Brown Double Exponential Smoothing

Table 03: Forecast Accuracy of Browns Double Exponential Model

Approach	Data Split	MAE	MAPE	MSE	RMSE
80/20 Split	In - Sam- ple	0.6	11.4	1.0	1.00
	Out- Of- Sam- ple	0.4	5.10	0.1	0.31
70/30 Split	In - Sam- ple	.62	10.8	0.9	.951
	Out- Of- Sam- ple	0.3	5.78	0.2	0.45

4.4 Model Estimation and Validation: - Holt’s Linear Exponential Smoothing Model

Table 04: Forecast Accuracy of Holt’s Linear Exponential Model

Approach	Data Split	MAE	MAPE	MSE	RMSE
80/20 Split	In - Sam- ple	0.5	9.39	0.8	0.90
	Out- Of- Sam- ple	2.4	12.4	0.5	0.72

4.5 Model Estimation and Validation: ARIMA Model

Before applying the ARIMA model, the unemployment rate series was examined for stationarity, which is essential for time series modeling. A time series is considered stationary if its statistical properties, such as mean, variance, and autocorrelation, do not change over time. A visual check of the time series plot indicated an inconsistent mean and the existence of a trend. To verify this statistically, the Augmented Dickey Fuller test was conducted using both validation methods (80/20 and 70/30).

Table 5. Augmented Dickey–Fuller Test for Unit Root at Level

Validation Approach	Test Level	Test Statistic	p-value	Decision
80/20 Split	Level	0.6068	0.9989	Fail to Reject Ho
80/20 Split	1st Difference	-4.9999	0.0004	Reject Ho
70/30 Split	Level	-1.4710	0.4670	Fail to Reject Ho
70/30 Split	1st Difference	4.70675	0.0010	Reject Ho

Table 6: Descriptive Statistics After First Differencing

Statistic	80/20 Split	70/30 Split
Min	-1.5000	-1.5000
Max	3.2000	3.2000
Mean	0.075862	0.0885
S. D	0.855092	0.9021
Skewness	1.713993	1.5967
Kurtosis	8.075347	7.2377

4.6 Model Identification

Table 07 : ARIMA Model Identification Using Information Criteria

Split	ARIMA Model	Log Likelihood	AIC	BIC
80/20	(0,1,0)	-36.1094	76.2188	78.9533
80/20	(0,1,1)	-36.1287	78.2575	82.3594
80/20	(1,1,0)	-36.1313	78.2626	82.3645
70/30	(0,1,0)	-33.7149	71.4297	73.9459
70/30	(0,1,1)	-33.7403	73.4806	77.2549
70/30	(1,1,0)	-33.7419	73.4838	77.2581

In both validation approaches, the ARIMA (0,1,0) model has the lowest AIC and BIC values, showing that it gives the best fit to the unemployment rate data. This model describes a random walk with drift, meaning the unemployment rate changes gradually over time without strong patterns or correlations. Therefore, the ARIMA (0,1,0) model chosen as the most suitable model for forecasting Pakistan's unemployment rate in both the 80/20 and 70/30 data splits.

4.7 Diagnostic Checking Of The Model

Table 08: - Modified Box–Pierce (Ljung–Box) Chi-Square Statistics for Residuals

Lag	12	24	36
Chi square	6.90	13.56	*
DF	11	23	*
P-value	0.807	0.939	*

Table 9. Forecast Accuracy (80/20 and 70/30 Splits, ARIMA)

ARIMA	MAE	MAPE	MSE	RMSE
In Sample (80%)	0.499	8.630	0.731	.855
Out-Of-Sample (20%)	0.669	9.196	0.289	0.538
In Sample (70%)	0.539	9.355	0.814	.902
Out-Of-Sample (30%)	0.421	7.012	0.263	0.513

4.8 Comparative Model Performance

Table 10. Out-of-Sample Forecast Accuracy Comparison

MO DE LS	80/20				70/30			
	M A E	M A PE	M S E	R M SE	M A E	M A PE	M S E	R M SE
Brown's Double	0.4	5.1	0.31	0.45	0.3	5.7	0.28	0.45
Holt's Linear	2.4	12.4	0.57	0.58	0.4	8.05	0.34	0.3
ARIMA	0.6	9.19	0.28	0.51	0.4	7.01	0.26	0.3

Four accuracy measures were implemented to compare the three forecasting outcomes of Brown's Double Exponential, Holt's Linear, and ARIMA (0,1,0) models. These metrics were MAE, MAPE, MSE, and RMSE. Higher predicting accuracy is shown by lower values of these metrics. The Findings indicate that the Brown's Double model performed both the 80/20 and 70/30 methods of validation due to its lowest MAE, MAPE, MSE.

4.9 Forecast of Unemployment Rate for the Years 2024–2030

The Brown's Double Exponential Smoothing model has been applied to forecast Pakistan's unemployment rate for the years between 2024 and 2030. This model was selected due to the performed well in recent accuracy evaluations, continuously giving the lowest forecast errors across all measures.

Table 12: - Forecasted Unemployment Rate in Pakistan (2024–2030)

Year	Forecasted unemployment rate (%)
2024	5.5
2025	5.4
2026	5.2
2027	5.0
2028	4.9
2029	4.7
2030	4.6

Figure 6. Observed vs. Forecasted Unemployment Rate Using Brown's Model (1986–2030)

4.10 Discussion

Brown's Double Exponential Smoothing, Holt's Linear Exponential Smoothing, and ARIMA (0,1,0) the three forecasting models that were examined in the study applying four metrics: MAE, MAPE, MSE, and RMSE. These indicators' smaller values result in accurate forecasts. The results disclosed under the both data splitting of 80/20 and 70/30 ratio, Brown's Double Exponential model came out to have the lowest accuracy errors and the best forecasting performance. This indicates that

forecasts were closer to the actual unemployment rates among all models. The ARIMA (0,1,0) model also performed well with moderate errors, while Holt's Linear model had the highest errors, making it least accurate. Generally, the Brown's Double Exponential model gave the most accurate forecasts for Pakistan's unemployment rate, followed by ARIMA (0,1,0), and then Holt's Linear model. These findings agree with earlier research. For instance, Tengaa et al. (2023) stated that the ARIMA model for Tanzania and verified that it performs well for non-stationary data after differencing, which matches the results of our research. Chia Xin Yi and Khalid (2022) also found that simple models like Holt's Linear can perform well when the data trend is unchangeable, which supports the strong performance of the Brown's Double Exponential model in this study. Other research, such as Gostkowski and Rokicki (2021) and Lip and Norliana (2021), indicate that, depending on the trends of the data, both exponential smoothing and ARIMA models may produce reliable results. Dritsakos and Klazoglou (2018) and Maria et al. (2018) found while simpler models can also work rather well, advanced models like SARIMA and GARCH can occasionally provide accuracy. Adenomon (2017) found that ARIMA worked well for forecasting unemployment in Nigeria and showed that unemployment tends to change slowly over time.

The results of the research support substantial evidence that both ARIMA and exponential smoothing models are efficient in forecasting unemployment. For Pakistan's unemployment data from 1986 to 2023, however, Brown's Double Exponential model gave the best and most accurate findings. This indicates that even a simple forecasting model may perform very well when the data shows an established and stable trend.

5 Conclusions

This study aimed to forecast Pakistan's unemployment rate using three models Brown's Double Exponential Smoothing, Holt's Linear Exponential Smoothing, and ARIMA estimating their performance based on key accuracy metrics. The Annual data from 1986 to 2023 were used and split into dual parts in- Sample and out-of-sample for model training and out-of-sample data for testing. This study revealed Brown's Double Exponential Smoothing the finest model for forecasting the unemployment rate in Pakistan. The forecasts for 2024 to 2030 suggest a slow decline in the unemployment rate, from 5.5% in 2024 to around 4.6% in 2030, observing a slow but positive improvement in employment situations if current trends continue. While forecasting the unemployment rate is a very tough and challenging task, it can also be a useful tool that helps with planning. Because it is challenging to create a forecast whose outcome would exactly match the actual value.

References

1. Adenomon, M. O. (2017). Modelling and forecasting unemployment rates in Nigeria using ARIMA model. *FUW Trends in Science and Technology Journal*, 2(1B), 525–531.
2. Box, G. E. P., & Jenkins, G. M. (1976). *Time series analysis: Forecasting and control*. San Francisco: Holden-Day.
3. Brown, R. G. (1963). *Smoothing, forecasting and prediction of discrete time series*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall.
4. Dritsakis, N., & Klazoglou, P. (2018). Forecasting unemployment rates in USA using Box-Jenkins methodology. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Issues*, 8(1), 9–15.
5. Holt, C. C. (1957). Forecasting trends and seasonal by exponentially weighted averages. *ONR Memorandum No. 52*, Carnegie Institute of Technology, Pittsburgh, USA. (Republished in *International Journal of Forecasting*, 20, 5–13, 2004)
6. Kyei, K. A., & Gyekye, K. B. (2011). Determinants of unemployment in Limpopo province in South Africa: Exploratory studies. *Journal of Emerging Trends in Economics and Management Sciences*, 2(1), 54–61.
7. Ljung, G. M., & Box, G. E. P. (1978). On a measure of a lack of fit in time series models. *Biometrika*, 65(2), 297–303.
8. Maqbool, M. S., Mahmood, T., Sattar, A., & Bhalli, M. N. (2013). Determinants of unemployment: Empirical evidences from Pakistan. *Pakistan Economic and Social Review*, 51(2), 191–208.
9. Mohd Lip, N., Mohd Rizuan, N. L. N., Iezudin, N. I., Mohamad, N. A., Mohd Rasyid, N. R., Hassan, F. A., & Ithnin, H. (2021). Comparative study of smoothing methods and Box-Jenkins model in forecasting unemployment rate in Malaysia. *Gading Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(1), 1–8.
10. Chia, X. Y., & bin Khalid, K. (2022). Forecasting analysis of unemployment rate in Malaysia based on the Naive, Holt's Linear Trend and Box-Jenkins models. *Enhanced Knowledge in Sciences and Technology*, 2(2), 011–020.
11. Gostkowski, M., & Rokicki, T. (2021). Forecasting the unemployment rate: Application of selected prediction methods. *European Research Studies*, 24(3), 985–1000.
12. Ramli, S. F., Firdaus, M., Uzair, H., & Zharif, A. (2018). Prediction of the unemployment rate in Malaysia. *International Journal of Modern Trends in Social Sciences*, 1(4), 27–36.
13. Ruth, H., et al. (2014). Understanding and overcoming the challenge of youth unemployment in Nigeria. *Review of*

- Public Administration and Management, 400(3614), 1–9.
14. Tengaa, P. E., Maiga, Y. M., & Mwasota, A. M. (2023). Modeling and forecasting unemployment rate in Tanzania: An ARIMA approach. *Journal of Applied Statistics and Econometrics*, 12(2), 88–102.
 15. Ullah, M., Su, K., & Jan, B. (2016). Forecasting, cointegration and causality analysis of unemployment using time series models. SSRN. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2863673>
 16. Vizie, T., & Kamarudin, A. N. (n.d.). Factors affecting unemployment rate and the forecasting trend. Unpublished manuscript.-*
 17. Trading Economics. (n.d.). Pakistan unemployment rate. Retrieved September 17, 2025, from <https://tradingeconomics.com/pakistan/unemployment-rate>